

Treatments were replicated four times with three seedboxes per replication. Each seedbox was divided into 4 sections to accommodate 10 treatments in a randomized complete block design.

Ten 10-cm-long rows were sown 5 cm apart in each section. Twenty seeds of moderately resistant IR36 or susceptible TN1 were sown in each row (see table). Six days after sowing (DAS) seedlings were thinned to 15/row.

The next day each section was

covered with a mylar film cage and the seedlings were infested with 3 3d-instar nymphs of TN1-reared GLH per seedling. Damage was recorded 7, 9, 11, and 15 d after infestation (DI).

The figure shows that the percentage of susceptible TN1 and moderately resistant IR36 did not substantially affect the damage ratings of either cultivar. Damage was significantly different only when there was 10% IR36:90% TN1. At that ratio, TN1

damage rated 6 at 15 DI compared to 8-9 in other treatments. When the percentage of TN1 decreased, damage rating per plant increased at 5 to 11 DI because of greater insect density on the few susceptible plants.

For a mass screening program with the objective of rejecting the bulk of susceptible material, the differences observed in this study are insignificant. *ℒ*

Reaction of IR varieties to Angoumois grain moth

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The Angoumois grain moth *Sitotroga cerealella* O. is a major pest of stored rice. IRRI varieties have been bred for resistance to several field insects, but not for resistance to storage pests. We evaluated IR varieties IR5 to IR54 for susceptibility to the Angoumois grain moth.

To disinfest grain, rough rice was frozen for 1 wk. Moisture content of each variety was reduced to 13%. Fifteen pair of moths were placed in each replication of 30 g of grain for 7 d, and then removed. Grain was kept in glass jars in the laboratory until insects began to emerge. The emerging insects were removed each day and counted.

The susceptibility index was based on total emerging adults and mean development period in days (D).

$$\text{Susceptibility index} = \frac{\text{Natural log F}}{D} \times 100$$

Grain weight loss was determined by

Mean number of insects that emerged.^a

Variety	Insects that emerged (no.) ^b	Susceptibility index ^b	Grain weight loss ^c (g)
IR5	52 cde	3.56 cd	0.76 cdefg
IR8	29 hijh	1.87 efg	0.67 efg
IR20	31 fghij	2.25 efg	0.50 fg
IR22	76 jk	1.61 fg	0.44 g
IR24	41 efghi	2.76 def	0.70 defg
IR26	29 ghijk	1.98 efg	0.46 g
IR28	30 ghijk	1.94 efg	0.58 efg
IR29	60 bcde	3.86 cd	1.28 ab
IR30	84 ab	5.25 b	1.38 a
IR32	28 jk	2.01 efg	0.60 efg
IR34	27 ijk	1.80 efg	0.64 efg
IR36	55 cde	3.64 cd	0.98 cd
IR38	43 defgh	2.88 de	0.72 defg
IR40	64 bcd	4.47 bc	1.06 bc
IR42	17 l	1.32 g	0.46 g
IR43	46 dcf	3.41 cd	0.82 cdef
IR44	31 fghij	2.02 efg	0.72 defg
IR45	44 defg	2.92 de	0.86 cde
IR46	19 kl	1.32 g	0.46 g
IR48	67 bc	4.26 bc	1.34 ab
IR50	120 a	7.52 a	1.52 a
IR52	30 jk	1.96 efg	0.58 efg
IR54	29 ghijk	1.87 efg	0.64 efg

^aAv of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bSusceptibility index is significantly correlated with loss of grain weight. $r = 0.922$. ^cPer 30-g weight before treatment.

weighing grains before and after the experiment.

Insect emergence was lowest in IR42 and IR46. The susceptibility indices differed significantly among varieties.

IR50 and IR30 had the highest values; IR42 and IR46, the lowest (see table). Grain weight loss was lowest in IR22, IR42, and IR46. *ℒ*

Seedbox screening tests to determine resistance to brown planthopper (BPH)

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We compared the standard seedbox screening test (SSST) and the modified seedbox screening test (MSST) for

identifying sources of resistance to BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) biotype 2. Twenty-five *O. sativa* varieties (see table) were sown 15 seeds/row in 20-cm-long rows in 60- × 40- × 7 cm seedboxes. Plant damage was rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

In SSST, each seedling was infested with 8 2d- to 3d-instar nymphs 7 d after sowing (DAS). The nymphs killed

susceptible cultivars 8-9 d after infestation (DI).

In MSST, each entry was infested with 3 2d- to 3d-instar nymphs at 10 DAS. The insects matured and produced F1 progeny that killed susceptible test plants at 25 DI.

Varieties that were susceptible in SSST and resistant in MSST were evaluated to determine their effect on

Damage ratings of selected cultivars to BPH biotype 2 in the SSST and MSST, IRRI.

IRRI accession no.	Variety	Damage rating ^a	
		SSST	MSST
4907	Birado	MR	R
4914	Toma 112	S	MR
4936	Ngasein thidat	S	S
5216	Mantika	S	S
5837	MTU14	S	R
5856	DA26	S	S
5886	Ngathalun CWR 10/9	S	S
5955	Hin trang	S	S
6002	Guttikusma	S	R
6008	Radin Siak 34	S	R
6029	Ptb 17	S	MR
6039	AKP8	S	S
6066	Bilugyun C32-1	S	S
6068	D52-37	S	S
6114	Molagasamba 18	MR	R
6145	MTU7	S	R
6162	American HS 1	S	R
6274	Ptb 9	MR	R
6291	Ptb 8	S	R
6339	BAM12	S	R
6353	MO 1	S	R
(R check)	IR60	R	R
(R check)	ASD7	MR	R
(MR check)	Triveni	S	MR
(S check)	IR26	S	S

^a R = resistant with rating of 1-3, MK = moderately resistant with rating of 5, and S = susceptible with rating of 7-9.

BPH biotype 2 population growth. Ten newly hatched nymphs were used to infest 25-d-old potted plants in a mylar film cage. BPH progeny per cage was counted at 35 DI.

Nine varieties were susceptible in both tests; 11 were susceptible in SSST but moderately resistant or resistant in MSST; and 4 were moderately resistant in SSST and resistant in MSST. Plant damage ratings of some varieties in SSST increased together, indicating insignificant differences in resistance (Fig. 1). In the MSST, the damage ratings of those varieties were significantly different, and older and younger plants had different resistance levels.

MO 1, Guttikusma, BAM12, MTU7, and MTU14, which were susceptible in SSST but resistant in MSST, have different levels of antibiosis, as shown by lower BPH population growth than in susceptible IR26 (Fig. 2). Antibiosis in those cultivars is apparently a factor that is measured in MSST but not in SSST.

MSST is a fast screening technique

1. Plant damage rating of rice varieties on SSST at indicated days after infestation with BPH biotype 2.

that can be used to mass screen varieties at tillering. Resistance at this stage is expected to be influenced by minor genes and increases with age. MSST, therefore, may identify more durable resistance than SSST, which identifies the major gene for resistance. *ℓ*

2. Varieties susceptible to BPH in MSST but resistant in SSST. IR60 is the resistant check; IR26, the susceptible check.

Mahaveera: a gall midge (GM)-resistant rice for coastal Karnataka

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Mahaveera (IET2886/Annapurna) was released for cultivation in coastal

Karnataka, where it will replace GMR 17 in transplanted uplands. Mahaveera (KKP 2) matures in 110 d and yields 4.1 t/ha, 37% more than GMR 17. Grains are long, bold, red kenneled, and suitable for parboiling, with 72% hulling. It is GM resistant, with 0.02% silvershoots compared to 33% for susceptible Annapurna and 4% for GMR 17 (see table). *ℓ*

GM incidence and yield performance of Mahaveera, 1979-83, Mandya, India.

Year	Silvershoots (%)			Yield (t/ha)		
	Mahaveera	Annapurna	GMR17	Mahaveera	Annapurna	GMR17
1979	0	32	1	4.3	3.3	3.5
1980	0	54	12	4.9	3.3	3.3
1981	0.1	30	4	4.4	3.4	3.5
1982	0	22	9	4.4	3.4	3.5
1983	0	28	5	2.7	1.9	1.6
Mean	0.02	33	6	4.1	3.1	3.0